

Hepatic biochemical, morphological and molecular effects of feeding microalgae and poultry oils to gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*)

Marta Carvalho^{*}, Daniel Montero, Silvia Torrecillas, Pedro Castro, María Jesús Zamorano, Marisol Izquierdo

Grupo de Investigación en Acuicultura (GIA), Instituto Universitario ECOAQUA, Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, Crta. Taliarte s/n, Telde 35214, Spain

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Fatty acids
Lipid metabolism
Novel lipid sources

ABSTRACT

The present work investigated how the combination of poultry oil with microalgae oils, rich in eicosapentaenoic acid and docosahexaenoic acid (ED diets) or n-6 docosapentaenoic acid and n-3 docosahexaenoic acid (DD diets) modulates hepatic lipid metabolism in gilthead sea bream juveniles. Diets were tested using two different fishmeal contents (15% and 7.5%) and compared against a fish oil-based diet (CTRL) and two negative control diets based on poultry oil as lipid source (PO diets). After 74 days of feeding, sea bream fed 15% FM ED or DD diets showed similar daily growth index to those fed CTRL, while those fed PO diets caused reduced growth. Fish livers reflected the highest contents in n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids when fed CTRL, ED or DD diets, which down-regulated *fas*, *scd-1a*, *fads2*, *lpl* and *cpt1*, reducing hepatic lipid accumulation and hepatocytes size. In contrast, fish fed PO diets showed the lowest deposition of n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids and the highest oleic acid in liver, leading with the highest hepatosomatic index due to increased liver lipids. Therefore, these fish revealed a severe hepatic steatosis associated with an increased expression of lipogenesis-related genes, particularly *fas*, *lpl* and *sbrep1*. Furthermore, PO diets seemed to activate desaturation pathways in fish livers, reflected by the highest accumulation of fatty acids that are products from desaturases and the highest *fads2* and *scd-1a* expressions. The reduction of the dietary fishmeal content to 7.5% lowered fish growth, although hepatic lipid metabolism seemed to be more affected by FO replacement than FM replacement. Combining microalgae with poultry oil could be an alternative lipid and essential fatty acid source to fish oil in marine fish diets.

1. Introduction

It is recognized worldwide that the replacement of fish-derived meals (FM) and oils (FO) in aquaculture feeds is mandatory for aquaculture sustainability, both from an economical and an environmental point of view. Therefore, in the past decades, finding alternative ingredients has justified an extensive research, in which plant raw materials have been in the forefront and have been reviewed elsewhere (Turchini et al., 2009; Montero and Izquierdo, 2010; Nasopoulou and Zabetakis, 2012). However, in relation to FO, its replacement by vegetable oils (VO) markedly reduces the dietary n-3 and n-6 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFA), particularly docosahexaenoic acid (DHA, 22:6n-

3), eicosapentaenoic acid (EPA, 20:5n-3) and arachidonic acid (ARA, 20:4n-6). Especially in marine fish, such as gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*), these FA are considered essential (EFA) and play important structural and functional roles in fish metabolism. This essentiality results from the inefficient biosynthetic activities of desaturases and elongases in saltwater species (Izquierdo and Koven, 2011; Tocher, 2015). Indeed, DHA, EPA and ARA are of pivotal physiological importance in vertebrates and their deficiency is associated with different health problems, from retarded development and growth to changes in lipid metabolism that cause nutritional diseases (Simopoulos, 2012; Spisni et al., 1998). For these reasons, the high inclusion of lipid sources devoid of n-3 LC-PUFA in fish diets often reduces growth, increases lipid

Abbreviations: ALA, linolenic acid; ARA, arachidonic acid; *cpt1*, carnitine palmitoyltransferase I; DGI, daily growth index; DHA, docosahexaenoic acid; DPA, docosapentaenoic acid; DW, dry weight; EFA, essential fatty acids; *elovl5*, fatty acyl elongase 5; EPA, eicosapentaenoic acid; *fads2*, fatty acyl desaturase 2; *fas*, fatty acid synthase; FO, fish oil; FM, fish meal; HSI, hepatosomatic index; LA, linoleic acid; LC-PUFA, long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids; *lpl*, lipoprotein lipase; MUFA, monounsaturated fatty acids; OA, oleic acid; *ppar-α*, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha; *scd-1a*, stearoyl-CoA desaturase-1; SFA, saturated fatty acids; *sbrep1*, 2, sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 and 2; VO, vegetable oil.

^{*} Corresponding author.

E-mail address: marta.ribeiro101@alu.ulpgc.es (M. Carvalho).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736073>

Received 14 July 2020; Received in revised form 16 October 2020; Accepted 16 October 2020

Available online 24 October 2020

0044-8486/© 2020 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

accumulation, particularly in liver, and, in severe cases, may lead to fish death (Spisni et al., 1998; Caballero et al., 2004). Furthermore, liver plays a central role in physiology, regulating lipid synthesis and catabolism (reviewed in Bradbury, 2006). Therefore, lipid homeostasis requires maintaining the balance between lipogenesis and lipolysis, that is achieved by a range of transcription factors and genes, which in turn, can be regulated by dietary fatty acids (Morais et al., 2011; Houston et al., 2017).

To reduce the dependence on FM and FO and counterbalance the negative effects of some VO in farmed fish, novel cost-effective lipid sources are being obtained from microorganisms, genetically modified plants or animal fats (Naylor et al., 2009; Adarme-Vega et al., 2014; Betancor et al., 2016; Tocher et al., 2019; Campos et al., 2019). Microalgae are among the most promising lipid sources, mainly due to its high EPA and/or DHA content (Shah et al., 2018). However, their high production costs constrain their use in fish diets to very early life stages, when EFA requirements are higher (Eryalçin et al., 2015). The consumer demand for n-3 LC-PUFA has resulted in an increased need of fish products. Successful replacement of FO was achieved with microalgae in salmonids at later stages of development (Santigosa, 2019; Kousoulaki et al., 2020). Other studies have successfully replaced FO, completely or partially by microalgae in different fish species, such as European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) (Tibaldi et al., 2015; Haas et al., 2016), olive flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*) (Qiao et al., 2014) or Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) (Sarker et al., 2016). However, in gilthead sea bream juveniles or older stages, the studies have focused more on the use of microalgae as additives or as FM replacers, than as FO substitutes (Cerezuela et al., 2012; Vizcaíno et al., 2014).

The growing quest to maintain the economic sustainability of aquaculture likely forces the use of microalgae products combined with other cheaper and more available sources such as poultry oil (PO). PO shows a competitive price and availability and has a high potential as energy source given its high saturated (SFA) and monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA) contents but lacks n-3 LC-PUFA (Rosenlund et al., 2001; Higgs et al., 2006; Hatlen et al., 2015). It has been incorporated as supplemental lipid source or partial replacer of FO in diets for some aquaculture species (Higgs et al., 2006; Hatlen et al., 2015; Turchini et al., 2013; Liland et al., 2015; Salini et al., 2015; Campos et al., 2019). A recent study by our research group found similar growth performance and enhanced fillet DHA deposition in gilthead sea bream fed a blend of microalgae oils and PO when compared to those fed FO (Carvalho et al., 2020). However, how these two lipid sources or their combination modulate hepatic lipid metabolism pathways in fish has not yet been investigated. Therefore, the aim of the present study was to investigate the nutritional regulation effects of totally replacing FO by a blend of microalgae oils, either DHA and EPA or DPA-rich, with PO on hepatic tissue of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) juveniles. For that, biochemical, histological and molecular responses were assessed.

The few studies conducted on the concomitant replacement of FM and FO reported an interaction between dietary protein and lipid sources on fish metabolism (Dias et al., 2005, 2009; Benedito-Palos et al., 2007; Torrecillas et al., 2017). Thus, we further investigated the possible role of the simultaneous replace of FM and FO on fish hepatic lipid metabolism, the former by increasing the dietary content of vegetable meals and the latter using the same microalgae and PO combinations as replacers of FO.

2. Methods

2.1. Ethical approval

All the protocols involving animals in this experiment were strictly conducted according to the European Union Directive (2010/63/EU) and Spanish legislation (RD 1201/2005) on the protection of animals for scientific purposes, at ECOAQUA-UI from University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain). All procedures were approved by

the Canary Island Council of Agriculture, Fishing and Water and the Bioethical Committee of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (reference OEBA-ULPGC-21/2018).

2.2. Diets

A total of 7 experimental diets were formulated with similar lipid and protein contents. A control diet (CTRL) was formulated to mimic practical diets used in gilthead sea bream culture, containing 15% of FM and 71.5% of a blend of vegetable meals, as well as 5% of FO and 7.92% of rapeseed oil. Three other experimental diets were based on CTRL diet but totally replaced FO by a combination of PO and one of two microalgae oils, either rich in EPA and DHA (15% FM ED) or DHA and n-6 docosapentaenoic acid (DPA) (15% FM DD) (Gren Oil, Veramaris, Netherlands and DHA Natur Oil, Archer Daniels Midland, USA, respectively). Three other experimental diets were formulated with the same lipid sources, in parallel with the replacement of 50% FM (7.5% FM ED, 7.5% FM DD or 7.5% FM PO), by increasing the vegetable meals content. For each level of FM, a diet replacing FO by only PO was formulated in order to evaluate the effects of the PO as sole replacer of FO (15% FM PO and 7.5% FM PO). Feeds were manufactured by Skretting ARC Feed Technology Plant (Stavanger, Norway) at a pellet size of 1 mm and shipped to the ECOAQUA Institute laboratories (Canary Islands, Spain). Diets composition are detailed in Table 1 and fatty acid profiles are presented in Table 2.

2.3. Feeding trial and fish performance

Gilthead sea bream fingerlings (initial body weight of 2.50 ± 0.01 g, mean \pm SE) were allocated, at a stocking density of 0.55 kg m^{-3} , in 21 fiberglass cylindrical tanks with 250 L volume supplied with filtered sea water, continuous air infusion and constant temperature (23.06 ± 0.33 °C) and dissolved oxygen ($6.36 \pm 0.18 \text{ mg L}^{-1}$). One experimental diet was randomly assigned to each tank. Triplicate tanks were fed each diet ($n = 3$). Fish were fed to visual apparent satiety 3 times a day, 6 days per week, for 74 days. At the end of the experimental trial, all fish were individually weighed to calculate the Daily Growth Index ($\text{DGI} = (\text{Final body weight}^{1/3} - \text{Initial body weight}^{1/3}) / \text{days} * 100$). Other details on growth performance, nutrient utilization and fillet fatty acid deposition of sea bream fed these diets containing microalgae and PO were previously described (Carvalho et al., 2020). The present study focused on the effect of these lipid sources on hepatic lipid metabolism, which in turn, could contribute to explain fish growth performance. For that purpose, fish were fasted for 24 h, and then 15 fish per tank were euthanized with an excess of clove oil to collect liver samples for different analysis. Livers were weighed to calculate hepatosomatic index in each fish using the following formula: Hepatosomatic index (HSI, %) = (liver weight / body weight) * 100.

2.4. Diets and hepatic biochemical composition

For diet samples, protein, ash and moisture contents were additionally analyzed according A.O.A.C. (2000). Liver samples from 5 animals per tank were collected and pooled. All samples were homogenized, and lipids from diet and liver tissue were extracted with chloroform/methanol (2:1 v/v) (Folch et al., 1957). Fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) were obtained by transmethylolation of lipids (Christie, 1989), which were then separated by gas liquid chromatography (Izquierdo et al., 1990), quantified by a flame ionization detector (Finnigan Focus SG, Thermo electron Corporation, Milan, Italy) and identified comparing with previously characterized standards.

2.5. Gene expression in liver

2.5.1. RNA extraction, quantification and complementary DNA synthesis
A central portion of liver tissue from 5 fish per tank were collected in

Table 1
Formulation and proximate composition of the experimental diets.

	Lipid source						
	15%FM			7.5%FM			
Ingredients (%)	CTRL	ED	DD	PO	ED	DD	PO
Fish meal ^a	15.00	15.00	15.00	15.00	7.50	7.50	7.50
Wheat ^a	12.30	12.43	12.13	11.43	9.90	9.52	10.88
Corn gluten ^a	6.58	6.12	6.20	10.00	10.00	10.00	10.00
Hi-pro soya ^a	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	8.00	8.00	5.00
Wheat gluten ^a	17.71	18.02	17.92	15.38	18.25	17.00	17.72
Soya protein concentrate ^a	25.00	25.00	25.00	25.00	27.50	29.00	30.00
Faba beans ^a	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00	5.00
Fish oil ^a	5.28	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Rapeseed oil ^a	7.92	7.60	5.69	7.29	7.52	5.58	7.57
Veramaris algal oil ^b	0.00	2.46	0.00	0.00	2.76	0.00	0.00
DHA Natur oil ^c	0.00	0.00	3.67	0.00	0.00	4.11	0.00
Poultry oil ^f	0.00	3.16	3.92	5.70	3.38	4.09	6.12
Vitamin premix ^{d,e}	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Mineral premix ^{d,e}	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
Microalgae: PO	–	1:1.3	1:1.1	–	1:1.2	1:1	–
Proximate analysis (% wet weight)							
Crude protein	49.31	48.35	48.06	50.18	49.31	49.14	50.38
Crude lipids	18.19	17.53	18.23	17.50	17.92	17.32	17.58
Neutral lipids (% of total lipids)	89.32	89.91	90.15	91.96	90.37	90.00	94.17
Polar lipids (% of total lipids)	10.68	10.09	9.85	8.04	9.63	10.00	5.83
Moisture	6.60	8.23	7.85	8.28	8.05	7.09	7.67
Ash	4.66	4.51	4.70	4.64	4.60	4.19	3.94
Starch (theoretical value)	10.03	10.04	10.18	9.87	8.64	8.52	9.05
Fiber (theoretical value)	2.53	2.53	2.53	2.54	2.78	2.85	2.81

^a Skretting AS (Norway).^b Veramaris algal oil (Veramaris, The Netherlands).^c DHA Natur oil (ADM Animal Nutrition, USA).^{d,e} Include vitamins and minerals; Trouw Nutrition, Boxmeer, the Netherlands, proprietary composition Skretting ARC,^f Poultry oil: Sonac. B.V. The Netherlands.

RNA later (Sigma-Aldrich, Madrid, Spain) and stored at -80°C until analysis. Total RNA was extracted from livers using the RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). Briefly, samples were homogenized with the TissueLyzer-II (Qiagen) with TRI Reagent (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, MO, USA) and centrifuged with chloroform at 12000 g for 15 min, at 4°C . The RNA phase was mixed with 75% ethanol and transferred into a RNeasy spin column, using RW1 and RPE buffers (Qiagen) to purify RNA bonded to a membrane obtaining purified RNA which was then eluted with 25 μL of RNase-free water. The NanoDrop 1000 Spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, Wilmington, DE, USA) and Gel Red™ staining (Biotium Inc., Hayward, CA) on 1.4% agarose electrophoresis gel were used to determine the quantity and integrity of RNA, respectively.

Complementary DNA (cDNA) was synthesized using iScriptcDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA) according to manufacturer's instructions using an iCycler thermal cycler (Bio-Rad).

2.5.2. RT-qPCR analysis

Liver mRNA levels of lipid metabolism-related genes, including *fatty acyl desaturase 2 (fads2)*, *fatty acyl elongase 5 (elovl5)*, *stearoyl-CoA*

Table 2
Fatty acid (g/100 g total fatty acids) composition of the experimental diets.

	Oil source						
	15% FM			7.5% FM			
Fatty acid	CTRL	ED	DD	PO	ED	DD	PO
14:0	2.05	0.73	1.33	0.72	0.39	1.30	0.82
14:1n-7	0.40	0.59	0.34	0.08	0.16	0.05	0.08
14:1n-5	0.37	0.52	0.35	0.03	0.19	0.06	0.03
15:0	0.45	0.41	0.35	0.10	0.16	0.15	0.08
15:1n-5	0.29	0.42	0.36	0.03	0.16	0.02	0.02
16:0ISO	0.37	0.49	0.40	0.03	0.19	0.07	0.03
16:0	9.72	8.80	10.51	11.59	9.41	12.09	13.08
16:1n-7	2.51	1.24	1.42	1.90	0.87	1.43	2.13
16:1n-5	0.31	0.64	0.38	0.06	0.15	0.02	0.03
16:2n-4	0.44	0.59	0.52	0.07	0.17	0.10	0.11
17:0	0.49	0.00	0.41	0.06	0.17	0.05	0.05
16:3n-4	0.28	0.68	0.35	0.11	0.24	0.09	0.10
16:3n-3	0.31	0.65	0.49	0.04	0.26	0.07	0.02
16:3n-1	0.28	0.42	0.46	0.05	0.32	0.05	0.01
16:4n-3	0.54	0.55	0.44	0.13	0.22	0.06	0.07
18:0	2.72	2.48	2.70	3.40	2.92	2.95	3.50
18:1n-9	30.01	28.16	29.26	39.78	33.58	34.87	40.78
18:1n-7	2.68	1.94	1.73	2.38	2.09	1.88	2.38
18:1n-5	0.37	0.47	0.47	0.07	0.15	0.08	0.05
18:2n-9	0.41	0.49	0.39	0.00	0.18	0.02	0.02
18:2n-6	15.74	15.52	16.36	23.16	19.44	19.69	24.58
18:2n-4	0.32	0.62	0.41	0.03	0.20	0.03	0.00
18:3n-6	0.23	0.94	0.52	0.08	0.19	0.15	0.11
18:3n-4	0.34	0.53	0.49	0.10	0.23	0.06	0.06
18:3n-3	5.02	4.30	3.61	5.29	4.63	4.04	5.27
18:3n-1	0.29	0.47	0.46	0.00	0.26	0.03	0.03
18:4n-3	0.94	0.57	0.53	0.39	0.29	0.23	0.20
20:0	0.68	0.73	0.50	0.52	0.85	0.41	0.42
20:1n-9	0.37	0.41	0.43	0.18	0.21	0.14	0.11
20:1n-7	2.33	2.20	1.91	1.96	1.77	1.29	1.36
20:1n-5	0.47	0.47	0.41	0.17	0.22	0.10	0.07
20:2n-9	0.30	0.56	0.35	0.05	0.23	0.04	0.06
20:2n-6	0.32	1.10	0.56	0.27	0.32	0.13	0.16
20:3n-9	0.28	0.00	0.00	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.00
20:3n-6	0.32	0.66	0.58	0.11	0.24	0.14	0.07
20:4n-6	0.59	0.80	0.48	0.32	0.50	0.40	0.21
20:3n-3	0.29	0.60	0.46	0.10	0.40	0.11	0.04
20:4n-3	0.44	0.72	0.64	0.11	0.38	0.22	0.07
20:5n-3	5.30	3.33	1.54	1.24	3.65	1.01	0.69
22:1n-11	2.37	2.26	1.56	1.94	1.45	1.02	0.93
22:1n-9	0.56	0.56	0.58	0.39	0.37	0.27	0.26
22:4n-6	0.36	1.08	1.32	0.15	0.25	0.11	0.06
22:5n-6	0.47	1.11	3.05	0.13	0.46	3.97	0.22
22:5n-3	1.31	1.04	1.09	0.31	0.68	0.31	0.13
22:6n-3	5.36	8.72	9.04	2.11	10.62	10.67	1.46
SFA	16.11	13.15	15.80	16.39	13.90	16.96	17.95
MUFA	43.02	39.89	39.20	48.96	41.35	41.21	48.23
n-9	31.93	30.18	31.01	40.58	34.57	35.34	41.23
n-6	17.79	21.21	22.88	24.29	21.40	24.59	25.41
n-6 LC-PUFA	2.06	4.75	5.99	0.98	1.77	4.75	0.72
n-3	19.51	20.49	17.84	9.72	21.12	16.73	7.96
n-3 LC-PUFA	12.70	14.41	12.77	3.87	15.73	12.32	2.39
n-3 LC-PUFA (% DW)	2.34	2.75	2.39	0.74	3.07	2.30	0.46
EPA + DHA	10.66	12.05	10.58	3.35	14.27	11.68	2.15
EPA/ARA	8.91	4.18	3.22	3.88	7.35	2.51	3.28
EPA/DHA	0.99	0.38	0.17	0.59	0.34	0.09	0.48
n-6/n-3	0.91	1.04	1.28	2.50	1.01	1.47	3.19

LC-PUFA, long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids; DW, dry weight; EPA, eicosapentaenoic acid; DHA, docosahexaenoic acid.

desaturase-1 a (scd-1a), *lipoprotein lipase (lpl)*, *fatty acid synthase (fas)*, *sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 and 2 (srebp-1, srebp-2)*, *carnitine palmitoyltransferase I (cpt-1)* and *peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (ppar- α)*, were determined by RT-qPCR in an iQ5 Multicolour Real-Time PCR detection system (Bio-Rad). *Elongation factor 1 alpha (ef1 α)*, was used as a housekeeping gene. All primers sequences are described in Table 3. RT-PCR conditions used were the following: a first step of 3 min 30 s at 95°C followed by 40 cycles of 15 s at 95°C , 30 s at 60.0°C , 30 s at 72°C , 1 min at 95°C , and a final 81 cycles of 10s from 55°C to 95°C . All

Table 3

Primers sequences used for RT-PCR analysis of lipid metabolism related-gene expression of gilthead sea bream hepatic tissue.

Gene	Primer Sequence (5'-3')	Accession n°
<i>ef1a</i>	F: CATGGTTGTGGACCCCTTCT R: TCCTGCACGACCATTCATTTTC	AF184170
<i>fads2</i>	F: GCAGGCGGAGAGCGACGGTCTGTTCC R: AGCAGGATGTGACCCAGGTGGAGGCAGAAG	AY055749
<i>elov15</i>	F: CCTCCTGGTCTCTACAAT R: GTGAGTGTCTGGCAGTA	AY660879
<i>scd-1a</i>	F: CGGAGGCGGAGGCGTTGGAGAAGAAG R: AGGGAGACGGCGTACAGGGCACCTATATG	JQ277703
<i>lpl</i>	F: CGTTGCCAAGTTGTGACCTG R: AGGGTGTCTGGTGTCTGTC	AY495672.2
<i>fas</i>	F: TGCCATTGCCATAGCACTCA R: ACCTTTGCCCTTTGTGTGGA	JQ277708.1
<i>srbp-1</i>	F: AGGGCTGACCACAACGTCTCCTCTCC R: GCTGTACGTGGGATGTGATGGTTGGG	JQ277709
<i>srbp-2</i>	F: GCTCACAAAGAAAATGGCCT R: CAAAACGTCCCTTCCCA	AM970922.1
<i>cpt-1</i>	F: GTGCCCTTGGTTCCTCATGATC R: TGATGCTTATCTGCTGCTGTTTG	JQ308822
<i>ppar-α</i>	F: TCTCTTCAGCCACCATCCC R: ATCCCAGCGTGTCTCTCC	AY590299

ef1a, elongation factor 1 alpha; *fads2*, fatty acyl desaturase 2; *elov15*, fatty acyl elongase; *scd-1a*, stearyl-CoA desaturase-1 a; *lpl*, lipoprotein lipase; *fas*, fatty acid synthase; *srbp1, 2*, sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 and 2; *cpt-1*, carnitine palmitoyltransferase I; *ppar-α*, peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha.

PCR reactions were carried out in a final volume of 20 μ L, with 7.5 μ L of Brilliant SYBR Green QPCR Master Mix (Bio-Rad Hercules, CA, USA), 0.6 μ L of each primer (10 mM), 5 μ L of cDNA (1:10 dilution) and 1.3 μ L of MiliQ water. MiliQ water also replaced cDNA in blank control reactions. Each run was ended with an analysis of melting curve leading to a melting peak specific for the amplified target DNA.

2.6. Hepatic tissue histomorphology

For histological examination of hepatic tissue morphology, the livers of 5 fish per tank were collected, dehydrated in a graded ethanol series and embedded in paraffin wax. Paraffin blocks were made and cut with a Leica microtome (Mod. Jung Autocut 2055; Leica, Nussloch, Germany) in 4 μ m sections, which were placed in slides and stained with haematoxylin and eosin (H&E) (Martoja and Martoja-Pierson, 1970) to visualization under a light microscope (BX51TF, Olympus, Tokyo, Japan).

2.6.1. Semi-quantitative histological examination

All slides were firstly blinded evaluated by three different researchers for describing general histomorphology of the hepatic tissue. A semi-quantitative score was used to evaluate hepatocyte lipid vacuolization: score 0–1 was considered as normal morphology of liver tissue, with none or very small lipid vacuoles within the hepatocytes; score 1–2 was considered as moderate hepatic steatotic alterations associated to a moderate lipid infiltration; and score 2–3 as severe steatotic alterations referring to a high lipid infiltration and large vacuoles within the hepatocytes.

2.6.2. Histometric analysis

Micrographs from each slide were taken using a Nikon Microphot-FXA microscope (Nikon Instruments Inc., Melville, NY, USA) incorporated with an Olympus DP50 camera (Olympus Optical Co. LTD, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo, Japan), The total area of 25 hepatocytes per specimen (375 hepatocytes per experimental diet) were measured, as well as the maximum and minimum length of these hepatocytes considering the hepatocyte nucleus as reference point and using arbitrary units. All the measurements were done with Image Pro-Plus software for Windows.

2.7. Statistical analyses

All data are presented as mean \pm SE, and each tank was treated as a replicate ($n = 3$ per treatment). Shapiro–Wilk and Levene's tests were used to test data normality and homogeneity of variances, respectively. A one-way ANOVA was applied to compare the experimental diets with the control diet. Additionally, a two-way ANOVA was used, excluding the control diet, to evaluate the effect of the oil source and fish meal independently in the novel diets and their potential interaction. Significant differences were detected when P -value was below 0.05 ($P < 0.05$) and if applicable, means were compared with Tukey's as post-hoc test (Tukey, 1949), except for steatosis degree scores in which a Mann-Whitney U test was applied. Data were also subjected to the best fit regressions (linear, exponential or logarithmic), which were also checked for significance at $P < 0.05$. Statistical treatment of the data was carried out using SPSS 21.0 software for macOS 10.15.

3. Results

3.1. Feeding trial and fish performance

After 74 days of feeding the experimental diets, sea bream fed both 15% FM ED and DD diets showed a similar growth than those fed CTRL diet, as indicated by the comparable daily growth indexes (DGI) among them (Fig. 1). However, fish fed 15% FM PO diet showed lower DGI than those fed CTRL, ED or DD diets ($P < 0.05$). Similar tendency was observed when comparing diets with 7.5% FM among them ($P < 0.05$; Table S1). However, a lowering effect in DGI occurred when FM was reduced to 7.5% FM ($P < 0.05$; Table S1). Fish fed the PO diets showed the highest ($P < 0.05$) HSI, whereas those fed ED or DD diets, at either 15 or 7.5% FM, presented similar HSI than those fed CTRL diet (Table 4). Similarly, the two-way ANOVA showed a significant effect of the lipid source on HSI ($P < 0.05$; Table S1). However, neither the dietary FM content nor the interaction between both dietary variables had a significant effect on HSI (Table S1). In addition, HSI linearly decreased with the increase of dietary n-3 LC-PUFA in % DW ($r^2 = 0.98$ and $P = 0.00$).

3.2. Liver biochemical composition

Lipid contents in liver were significantly higher in fish fed the PO diets than in those fed any of the other diets ($P < 0.05$; Table 4). Thus, liver lipid contents linearly decreased with the increase of dietary n-3 LC-PUFA in % DW ($r^2 = 0.89$ $P = 0.00$). Besides, HSI linearly increased with liver lipids ($r^2 = 0.88$ $P = 0.01$).

Liver fatty acid composition showed a tendency to mirror the dietary profiles for most fatty acids, including oleic acid (OA, 18:1n-9), EPA, n-6

Fig. 1. Daily growth indices of gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%), during the whole feeding period. Different letters denote significant differences among the experimental groups at the end of the trial, according to one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4

Hepatosomatic index (%), hepatic lipid content (% ww) and liver fatty acid composition (g/100 g total fatty acids) of gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%).

	Experimental diets													
	15% FM						7.5% FM							
	CTRL	ED		DD		PO		ED		DD		PO		
Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	
HSI (%)	1.47 ^{ab}	0.09	1.44 ^{ab}	0.09	1.48 ^{ab}	0.08	1.70 ^a	0.16	1.32 ^b	0.06	1.42 ^{ab}	0.07	1.77 ^a	0.08
Liver lipid (% ww)	20.44 ^b	1.08	20.24 ^b	0.88	20.01 ^b	1.53	29.16 ^a	1.16	21.05 ^b	0.65	19.38 ^b	2.38	26.97 ^a	2.19
Fatty acid (g/100 g total fatty acids)														
14:0	0.91 ^{ab}	0.16	0.67 ^a	0.01	0.64 ^a	0.02	0.65 ^a	0.01	0.61 ^{ab}	0.08	0.63 ^{ab}	0.03	0.50 ^b	0.02
14:1n-7	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00
14:1n-5	0.03	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
15:0	0.11 ^a	0.01	0.09 ^{abc}	0.00	0.08 ^{bcd}	0.00	0.07 ^{cd}	0.00	0.10 ^{ab}	0.01	0.08 ^{bcd}	0.00	0.06 ^d	0.00
15:1n-5	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00
16:0iSO	0.03 ^a	0.00	0.01 ^{ab}	0.00	0.01 ^{ab}	0.01	0.01 ^b	0.00	0.01 ^b	0.01	0.01 ^b	0.00	0.01 ^b	0.00
16:0	10.52	0.73	10.74	0.22	9.95	0.24	9.58	0.13	10.60	0.58	9.42	0.21	9.13	0.09
16:1n-7	2.35 ^a	0.14	1.77 ^{ab}	0.00	1.71 ^{ab}	0.04	1.96 ^b	0.01	1.73 ^{ab}	0.06	1.64 ^b	0.03	1.72 ^{ab}	0.04
16:1n-5	0.10 ^a	0.01	0.04 ^b	0.00	0.05 ^b	0.00	0.07 ^b	0.01	0.05 ^b	0.01	0.05 ^b	0.01	0.07 ^b	0.00
16:2n-4	0.13 ^a	0.00	0.04 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00
17:0	0.16 ^a	0.02	0.06 ^b	0.00	0.05 ^b	0.00	0.07 ^b	0.01	0.05 ^b	0.00	0.05 ^b	0.00	0.06 ^b	0.01
16:3n-4	0.18 ^a	0.01	0.13 ^{bcd}	0.00	0.12 ^{cd}	0.00	0.14 ^b	0.00	0.13 ^{bc}	0.01	0.11 ^d	0.00	0.12 ^{bcd}	0.00
16:3n-3	0.05 ^a	0.01	0.02 ^b	0.00	0.02 ^b	0.00	0.02 ^b	0.01	0.02 ^b	0.00	0.02 ^b	0.01	0.02 ^b	0.00
16:4n-3	0.07	0.01	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.21	0.2	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.00
18:0	6.16	0.40	5.47	0.09	5.70	0.00	5.52	0.10	5.38	0.03	5.33	0.22	5.99	0.28
18:1n-9	39.38 ^{bc}	1.47	39.39 ^{bc}	0.34	38.62 ^c	0.00	43.30 ^{ab}	0.31	39.93 ^{abc}	0.46	38.56 ^c	1.18	43.77 ^a	0.59
18:1n-7	3.41	0.18	2.58	0.03	2.56	0.00	2.97	0.03	2.25	0.34	2.38	0.12	1.98	0.99
18:1n-5	0.11 ^a	0.01	0.08 ^{bc}	0.00	0.07 ^{bc}	0.08	0.09 ^{ab}	0.00	0.08 ^{bc}	0.01	0.06 ^c	0.00	0.08 ^{bc}	0.00
18:2n-9	1.80 ^b	0.28	1.58 ^b	0.11	1.96 ^b	0.67	3.28 ^a	0.41	1.87 ^b	0.12	1.84 ^b	0.08	4.10 ^a	0.44
18:2n-6	14.00 ^c	0.37	16.70 ^{ab}	0.33	15.36 ^{bc}	0.07	17.50 ^{ab}	0.39	18.24 ^a	0.45	16.86 ^{ab}	0.46	17.12 ^{ab}	0.74
18:2n-4	0.17 ^a	0.01	0.04 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.04 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.01	0.03 ^b	0.00	0.03 ^b	0.00
18:3n-6	2.19 ^b	0.37	2.19 ^b	0.13	2.53 ^b	0.17	4.24 ^a	0.45	2.89 ^b	0.28	2.70 ^b	0.22	4.86 ^a	0.12
18:3n-4	0.13 ^a	0.00	0.06 ^b	0.00	0.05 ^b	0.66	0.07 ^b	0.00	0.05 ^b	0.01	0.05 ^b	0.00	0.06 ^b	0.00
18:3n-3	2.83 ^{abc}	0.16	3.11 ^a	0.06	2.37 ^c	0.00	2.61 ^{abc}	0.05	2.93 ^{ab}	0.07	2.47 ^{bc}	0.06	2.40 ^{bc}	0.19
18:4n-3	0.80	0.19	0.63	0.06	0.59	0.10	0.84	0.12	0.62	0.06	0.60	0.00	0.79	0.01
18:4n-1	0.08	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.22	0.21	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.04
20:0	0.25	0.04	0.23	0.03	0.19	0.09	0.19	0.01	0.18	0.01	0.19	0.03	0.19	0.01
20:1n-9	0.35 ^a	0.04	0.26 ^{bc}	0.01	0.27 ^{ab}	0.01	0.29 ^{ab}	0.02	0.16 ^d	0.01	0.17 ^{cd}	0.01	0.21 ^{bcd}	0.01
20:1n-7	1.41 ^a	0.20	1.21 ^{ab}	0.05	1.09 ^{abc}	0.02	0.94 ^{bc}	0.05	0.83 ^{bc}	0.07	0.80 ^{bc}	0.07	0.77 ^c	0.03
20:1n-5	0.16 ^a	0.03	0.08 ^b	0.00	0.08 ^b	0.00	0.09 ^b	0.00	0.07 ^b	0.00	0.08 ^b	0.00	0.09 ^b	0.00
20:2n-9	0.59 ^{ab}	0.04	0.63 ^a	0.08	0.57 ^{ab}	0.01	0.54 ^{ab}	0.02	0.27 ^b	0.03	0.26 ^b	0.07	0.48 ^{ab}	0.07
20:2n-6	0.42	0.07	0.42	0.04	0.39	0.01	0.36	0.03	0.77	0.42	0.32	0.03	0.34	0.03
20:3n-9	0.03 ^a	0.01	0.01 ^{ab}	0.00	0.00 ^b	0.02	0.01 ^{ab}	0.01	0.00 ^b	0.00	0.00 ^b	0.00	0.01 ^{ab}	0.00
20:3n-6	0.37 ^{ab}	0.01	0.41 ^{ab}	0.05	0.46 ^a	0.01	0.33 ^{ab}	0.02	0.24 ^b	0.02	0.32 ^{ab}	0.05	0.30 ^{ab}	0.05
20:4n-6	0.49 ^b	0.04	0.47 ^b	0.01	0.71 ^a	0.14	0.28 ^c	0.01	0.53 ^b	0.01	0.78 ^a	0.01	0.29 ^c	0.03
20:3n-3	0.16 ^a	0.02	0.16 ^a	0.01	0.12 ^{ab}	0.02	0.10 ^b	0.01	0.14 ^{ab}	0.01	0.10 ^b	0.01	0.10 ^b	0.01
20:4n-3	0.39	0.03	0.31	0.02	0.31	0.00	0.15	0.01	0.52	0.34	0.24	0.02	0.11	0.02
20:5n-3	2.44 ^a	0.58	1.78 ^{ab}	0.08	0.82 ^{bc}	0.06	0.51 ^c	0.02	1.45 ^{abc}	0.15	0.72 ^{bc}	0.09	0.38 ^c	0.07
22:1n-11	0.96 ^a	0.17	0.72 ^{ab}	0.07	0.71 ^{ab}	0.03	0.52 ^{bc}	0.02	0.35 ^{bc}	0.05	0.40 ^{bc}	0.07	0.32 ^c	0.01
22:1n-9	0.63 ^a	0.13	0.48 ^{ab}	0.02	0.46 ^{ab}	0.01	0.47	0.01	0.33 ^b	0.05	0.37 ^{ab}	0.04	0.40 ^{ab}	0.01
22:4n-6	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.09	0.04	0.07	0.00	0.08	0.03	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.00
22:5n-6	0.14 ^b	0.01	0.24 ^b	0.01	2.87 ^a	0.07	0.07 ^b	0.01	0.44 ^b	0.14	3.16 ^a	0.15	0.14 ^b	0.02
22:5n-3	0.99 ^a	0.17	0.74 ^{ab}	0.05	0.38 ^c	0.04	0.17 ^c	0.01	0.47 ^{bc}	0.04	0.31 ^c	0.04	0.14 ^c	0.03
22:6n-3	4.39 ^{bc}	0.57	6.24 ^{ab}	0.31	7.86 ^{ab}	0.02	1.71 ^c	0.11	5.04 ^{abc}	0.62	8.68 ^a	1.79	1.68 ^c	0.16
SFA	18.14 ^a	0.81	17.28 ^{ab}	0.18	16.62 ^{ab}	0.01	16.09 ^{ab}	0.21	16.94 ^{ab}	0.68	15.70 ^b	0.36	15.95 ^{ab}	0.37
MUFA	48.91 ^{ab}	2.03	46.65 ^{ab}	0.41	45.66 ^{ab}	0.11	50.76 ^a	0.33	45.83 ^{ab}	0.81	44.56 ^b	1.47	49.45 ^{ab}	0.58
n-9	42.76 ^b	1.38	42.34 ^b	0.37	41.88 ^b	0.05	47.89 ^a	0.24	42.56 ^b	0.63	41.21 ^b	1.25	48.96 ^a	0.97
n-6	17.71 ^c	0.49	20.53 ^b	0.25	22.41 ^{ab}	0.99	22.85 ^{ab}	0.18	23.20 ^a	0.65	24.24 ^a	0.43	23.10 ^a	0.73
n-6 PUFA	17.71 ^c	0.49	20.53 ^b	0.25	22.41 ^{ab}	0.53	22.85 ^{ab}	0.18	23.20 ^a	0.65	24.24 ^a	0.43	23.10 ^a	0.73
n-6 LC-PUFA	1.51 ^b	0.06	1.64 ^b	0.08	4.52 ^a	0.20	1.10 ^b	0.03	2.06 ^b	0.53	4.68 ^a	0.10	1.12 ^b	0.11
n-3	12.12 ^a	1.64	13.01 ^a	0.48	12.49 ^a	1.13	6.14 ^{bc}	0.07	11.41 ^{ab}	1.02	13.15 ^a	2.06	5.64 ^c	0.51
n-3 PUFA	12.12 ^a	1.64	13.01 ^a	0.48	12.49 ^a	1.13	6.14 ^{bc}	0.07	11.41 ^{ab}	1.02	13.15 ^a	2.06	5.64 ^c	0.51
n-3 LC-PUFA	8.37 ^a	1.29	9.23 ^a	0.44	9.49 ^a	1.16	2.64 ^{bc}	0.11	7.63 ^{ab}	0.86	10.04 ^a	1.93	2.41 ^c	0.29
EPA + DHA	6.83 ^{ab}	1.11	8.02 ^a	0.38	8.68 ^a	1.06	2.21 ^{bc}	0.10	6.49 ^{abc}	0.77	9.39 ^a	1.89	2.06 ^c	0.22
EPA/ARA	4.86 ^a	0.87	3.79 ^{ab}	0.18	1.15 ^{cd}	0.09	1.81 ^{cd}	0.06	2.75 ^{bc}	0.32	0.92 ^d	0.12	1.30 ^{cd}	0.12
EPA/DHA	0.54 ^a	0.09	0.29 ^b	0.01	0.10 ^c	0.00	0.30 ^b	0.02	0.29 ^b	0.01	0.08 ^c	0.01	0.22 ^{bc}	0.02
n-6/n-3	1.51 ^b	0.21	1.58 ^b	0.07	1.83 ^b	0.22	3.72 ^a	0.02	2.08 ^b	0.25	1.93 ^b	0.29	4.15 ^a	0.27
16:0/16:1	4.30 ^d	0.17	5.93 ^a	0.13	5.66 ^{ab}	0.08	4.73 ^{cd}	0.06	5.94 ^a	0.15	5.56 ^{ab}	0.12	5.12 ^{bc}	0.16
18:0/18:1	0.14	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.12	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.01
18:1/18:2(n-9)	23.45 ^{ab}	5.09	25.11 ^a	1.61	20.00 ^{abc}	1.74	13.58 ^{bc}	1.59	21.48 ^{abc}	1.29	21.06 ^{abc}	1.18	10.89 ^c	0.94
18:3/18:4(n-3)	3.97	0.93	5.03	0.5										

dietary pattern as expected (Table 4). This was the case for some products of different desaturases, for instance the higher values of 16:1n-5 and 18:1n-5, products of SCD-1a found in fish fed PO than in those fed ED or DD diets, when compared with the lower values in the respective diets ($P < 0.05$). Accordingly, PO fish showed a lower 16:0/16:1 ratio than those fed DD or ED diets ($P < 0.05$). The same tendency was noted on 18:2n-9, 20:2n-9, 18:3n-6, 20:3n-6, and, to a slighter extent on 18:4n-3, all potential products of FADS2. Besides, despite dietary linoleic acid (LA, 18:2n-6) levels were higher in PO diets, fish fed these diets did not show significant differences in LA in comparison to those fed ED or DD diets. The same was true for linolenic acid (ALA, 18:3n-3), which was the highest in 7.5% FM PO diet, but was the second lowest in livers of fish fed this diet. Furthermore, a lower 18:1n-9/18:2n-9 ratio was found in fish fed PO diets, in particular in those fed 7.5% FM PO ($P < 0.05$), and a tendency to present lower 18:3n-3/18:4n-3 ratio in these fish as well. However, these tendencies were not so marked for elongation products, such as 20:2n-6 or 20:3n-3, where contents in fish liver reflect the dietary patterns (Table 4). Interestingly, sea bream fed DD diets presented the highest hepatic 20:4n-6 contents despite the low dietary levels ($P < 0.05$; Table 4).

The dietary FM content significantly influenced some liver FA, increasing 18:3n-6, 20:4n-6 and 22:5n-6 in fish fed 7.5% FM diets, which resulted in an increasing of total n-6 and n-6 LC-PUFA in these fish ($P < 0.05$; Table S1). On the contrary, it decreased the contents of 20:3n-6, 20:5n-3, 22:1n-11 and 22:5n-3 in sea bream fed 7.5% FM diets when compared to those fed 15% FM ($P < 0.05$; Table S1). However, there was not a significant combined effect of the dietary FM content and the lipid source in liver fatty acid composition of fish (Table S1).

3.3. Gene expression of lipid metabolism-related markers

3.3.1. Lipogenic pathway

Sea bream fed CTRL, ED and DD diets presented similar relative expression of *srebp1* and *fas* (Fig. 2), whereas fish fed PO diets showed significant higher ($P < 0.05$) *fas* expression, particularly those fed 7.5% FM PO diet, and a tendency to higher *srebp1* expression (78% higher than fish fed 7.5% ED for instance) (Fig. 2). Indeed, *srebp1* and *fas* linearly decreased with the increase of the dietary n-3 LC-PUFA ($r^2 = 0.75$ $P = 0.01$ and $r^2 = 0.85$ $P = 0.00$, respectively) and DHA ($r^2 = 0.75$ $P = 0.01$ and $r^2 = 0.77$ $P = 0.01$, respectively). No significant differences were observed for *srebp2* expression among sea bream fed the different diets (Fig. 2).

3.3.2. Elongation and desaturation pathways

Sea bream fed the ED or DD diets showed similar *scd-1a* or *fads2* relative expression compared to those fed the CTRL diet (Fig. 3). In contrast, in fish fed PO diets, *scd-1a* was significantly up-regulated ($P < 0.05$). Although no significant differences were detected, probably due to the large inter-variation in fish gene expression, a tendency to present higher (70–92%) mRNA levels of *fads2* was also noted in fish fed PO when compared to those fed CTRL, ED or DD diets (Fig. 3). Indeed, both *scd-1a* and *fads2* presented a significant logarithmic correlation with the dietary dry weight of n-3 LC-PUFA ($r^2 = 0.86$, $P = 0.00$ for *scd-1a*; $r^2 = 0.73$, $P = 0.01$ for *fads2*). Additionally, *scd-1a* was particularly highly correlated with the dietary 16:0 ($r^2 = 0.77$ $P = 0.01$) and 18:0 ($r^2 = 0.95$ $P = 0.00$), but also logarithmic with the dietary DHA ($r^2 = 0.73$ $P = 0.01$), whereas *fads2* was positively correlated with the dietary OA ($r^2 = 0.80$ $P = 0.01$), LA ($r^2 = 0.84$ $P = 0.00$), ARA ($r^2 = 0.86$ $P = 0.00$) and EPA ($r^2 = 0.73$ $P = 0.01$). In contrast, no tendency was clear for *elovl5* expression (Fig. 3).

3.3.3. Lipolytic pathway

Expression of *lpl* was 4–5 times higher in fish fed 7.5% FM PO than in fish fed the CTRL diet, despite the lack of significant differences ($P > 0.05$). (Fig. 4). Additionally, *lpl* was linearly increased with the dietary OA ($r^2 = 0.89$ $P = 0.01$) and LA ($r^2 = 0.84$ $P = 0.00$) ($r^2 = 0.86$ $P = 0.00$). For *cpt1* expression, similar mRNA values were shown among CTRL, ED and DD diets, but a higher relative expression in fish fed 7.5% FM PO than in those fed the other diets could be noted ($P < 0.05$; Fig. 4). No significant differences were observed regarding *ppara*.

For all the different genes studied the two-way ANOVA showed that the dietary oil source was the major driver in the differences found in gene expression (Table S1). Whereas the expressions of the studied genes were not affected by the dietary content of FM (Table S1). In addition, no interaction effect was observed between these two dietary variables for any of the genes studied (Table S1).

3.4. Hepatic tissue histomorphology

Morphologically, sea bream fed ED and DD diets showed lower cytoplasmatic lipid vacuolization that, when present, was in the form of micro-vacuolization, with smaller eosinophilic hepatocytes and prominent basophilic nuclei (Fig. 4). This hepatocyte vacuolization was tentatively increased ($P = 0.05$) in those fish fed CTRL diet as showed by the slight higher degree of steatosis and hepatocyte size, but more significantly ($P = 0.00$) in those fed PO diets, which showed a strong macro-vacuolization leading to the highest steatosis level and the largest

Fig. 2. Hepatic relative expression of lipogenic pathway related genes in gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%). Different letters denote significant differences among the experimental groups at the end of the trial, according to one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 3. Hepatic relative expression of elongation and desaturation pathway related genes in gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%). Different letters denote significant differences among the experimental groups at the end of the trial, according to one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 4. Hepatic relative expression of lipolytic pathway related genes in gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%). Different letters denote significant differences among the experimental groups at the end of the trial, according to one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

hepatocytes (Fig. 5) (Table 5). Indeed, hepatocyte size increase linearly with the increase of liver lipids ($r^2 = 0.93$ $P = 0.00$), as well with the decrease of the dietary n-3 LC-PUFA ($r^2 = 0.88$ $P = 0.00$) and the increase of the dietary OA ($r^2 = 0.78$ $P = 0.01$). Furthermore, both hepatocyte size and liver lipids were strongly correlated and linearly increased with the expression of *fas* ($r^2 = 0.90$ $P = 0.00$ and $r^2 = 0.89$ $P = 0.00$, respectively) and logarithmic correlated with the expression of *scd-1a* ($r^2 = 0.86$ $P = 0.01$ and $r^2 = 0.74$ $P = 0.00$, respectively). Similarly, hepatocyte size also showed a linear increased with the increase in *sreb1* expression ($r^2 = 0.69$ $P = 0.02$).

Again, the two-way ANOVA showed only significant differences for lipid source, adding strength to the results already observed for one-way ANOVA and with FM content or an interaction being less influencers of liver morphology (Table S1).

4. Discussion

The decrease in dietary n-3 LC-PUFA in feeds based on low FO and high VO inclusions affects fish metabolism and health, particularly in marine species (reviewed in Montero and Izquierdo, 2010). Therefore, novel n-3 LC-PUFA sources are necessary to promote aquafeeds production and aquaculture sustainability. In fact, EFA-deficiency causes

many alterations in metabolism, including different lipid pathways, what may negatively affect fish performance. Optimum dietary n-3 LC-PUFA levels for gilthead sea bream juveniles were previously estimated at 1.3–1.6% DW (Izquierdo, 2005; Houston et al., 2017). Specifically, optimum dietary levels for this species were estimated to be 0.6–0.7% DW for DHA and 0.6–0.9% DW for EPA (Izquierdo, 2005). Accordingly, in the present study, FO, ED and DD diets covered the specific requirements for n-3 LC-PUFA and DHA of gilthead sea bream. Even though, microalgae diets (ED and DD) presented EPA contents under the optimum levels estimated for the species, particularly in DD diets. Despite this, similar growth was observed among sea bream fed either 15% FM microalgae diets (ED or DD) and FO diet. These results are in agreement with the effectiveness of DHA as a growth promoter in comparison to EPA (Watanabe, 1993; Izquierdo, 1996, 2005). Furthermore, the present results indicated the potential of microalgae oils, DHA-rich, as effective n-3 LC-PUFA sources for sea bream juveniles, as it was recently found for salmonids juveniles (Peterson et al., 2019; Santigosa, 2019; Kousoulaki et al., 2020).

In addition, it is well recognized that fish tissue fatty acid composition usually reflects the dietary composition (Covey and Sargent, 1972). In the present study, livers from sea bream fed ED or DD diets mirrored the high dietary DHA contents, while those from fish fed FO (CTRL diet)

Fig. 5. Liver histological appearance of gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%) (stained with H&E; scale 20 µm).

Table 5

Histological parameters of hepatic tissue of gilthead sea bream fed novel lipid sources (microalgae and poultry oils) as replacers of FO under two dietary contents of fish meal (15 and 7.5%).

	Experimental diets													
	15% FM						7.5% FM							
	CTRL		ED		DD		PO		ED		DD		PO	
	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE	Mean	SE
Steatosis degree	2.30 ^b	0.13	2.05 ^b	0.14	2.04 ^b	0.14	2.38 ^b	0.14	2.08 ^b	0.17	2.04 ^b	0.17	2.75 ^a	0.10
Hepatocyte area	45.82 ^{bc}	1.98	35.67 ^c	2.61	35.63 ^c	2.81	70.97 ^{ab}	7.19	42.00 ^c	2.90	39.51 ^c	0.54	71.14 ^a	10.64

Different letters denote significant differences among the experimental groups at the end of the trial, according to one-way ANOVA ($P < 0.05$).

showed the highest content of EPA. Therefore, the highest hepatic DHA contents of sea bream fed microalgae oils in the present study seemed to be the main reason for the smallest alterations in fish hepatic histology. Noticeable, fish fed ED or DD diets showed a very low lipid infiltration, reflected in a microvacuolization of the hepatocytes and the lowest hepatocyte area. This was also consistent with the lowest steatosis degree, liver lipid contents and HSI found in these fish, as reported in other marine species fed diets meeting their EFA requirements (Ibeas et al., 1994; Kjaer et al., 2008; Carvalho et al., 2018). Indeed, n-3 LC-PUFA has been related to a reduced hepatic lipid infiltration by maintaining lipid metabolism homeostasis, since they reduce triacylglycerides synthesis (Berge et al., 1999). Furthermore, n-3 LC-PUFA increase the expression of microsomal transfer protein or apolipoprotein A1 (Kjaer et al., 2008), whereas down-regulate adipophilin expression, which is a molecular marker of intracellular lipid accumulation (Leaver et al., 2008). In agreement, all the genes related with lipogenesis and lipolytic pathways metabolism analyzed in the present study, showed similar relative expression among sea bream fed microalgae oils and FO. This suggest that the total replacement of FO is possible by blending microalgae oils with other EFA-devoid lipid sources, usually cheaper and more available, such as PO, with no major impact in sea bream hepatic lipid metabolism. Given the still high production costs of microalgae, a detailed economical study of the experimental diets containing both microalgae and poultry oils would be of interest. Furthermore, the use of microalgae oils could even improve liver health status by reducing lipid vacuolization, even when comparing with FO (CTRL diet). Further studies are needed to determine the potential positive long-term effects of microalgae sources. Besides, the highest n-6 DPA contents were found in livers of sea bream fed DD diets, a FA reported in high amounts in *Schizochytrium* sp. (Jiang et al., 2004; Zhang et al., 2017). Interestingly, these fish also presented the highest liver ARA contents, contrary to their lowest dietary levels, suggesting a retroconversion of the excessive n-6 DPA to ARA, as reported previously in gilthead sea bream larvae fed this microalga (Ganuza and Izquierdo, 2007).

The total replacement of FO by PO alone led to the lowest sea bream growth in the present study, probably associated to an EFA-deficiency. In fact, the replacement by PO was not sufficient to maintain n-3 LC-PUFA optimum levels for this species, being deficient in both DHA and EPA (Izquierdo, 2005). This is in agreement with the increased HSI and liver lipids in these fish, common indicators of EFA-deficiency in teleost (Verreth et al., 1994). Hepatomegaly associated to an increase in liver lipids can be the result of an excess in dietary lipids, surpassing the liver storage capacity, but also of an inadequate dietary fatty acid composition by altering hepatic lipid metabolism and leading to steatosis (Spisni et al., 1998). This pathologic condition compromises fish metabolic utilization of nutrients and energy and, consequently, fish health and performance (Spisni et al., 1998; Verreth et al., 1994; Montero and Izquierdo, 2010). In line, sea bream of the present study developed a severe steatosis, characterized by a high lipid macrovacuolization and the highest hepatocyte area. Indeed, hepatocyte size, hepatic lipids and HSI were all strongly linearly correlated with the dietary n-3 LC-PUFA. Likewise, livers from fish fed PO diets reflected the lowest dietary n-3 LC-PUFA and the highest hepatic OA, in agreement with previous studies in other fish species fed poultry fats (Turchini et al., 2009; Campos et al., 2019). The accumulation of both OA and LA were shown to be major FA influencers of the appearance of hepatic steatosis in fish (Caballero et al., 2004). Furthermore, due to the high molecular weight of OA, the influx of this FA inside the hepatocyte was sufficient to create a large lipid droplet (Bradbury, 2006), which was observed in fish fed PO diets. In addition, OA seems to be slowly metabolized in liver of marine fish, since the excess of this FA is mainly degraded in peroxisomes and marine fish has a lower capacity to replicate this organelle, contributing to the lipid accumulation in the hepatocytes (Caballero et al., 2002).

Lipid metabolism homeostasis is achieved by an equilibrium between anabolic and catabolic pathways. In the present study, the total

replacement of FO by PO significant altered lipid metabolism in liver of sea bream, particularly in relation to lipogenic processes. PO induced an up-regulation of hepatic *srebp1* and *fas*, both genes involved in lipid synthesis. *Srebp1* regulates *de novo* synthesis of FA, having a wide range of targets, including *fas*, whose enzymatic product synthesizes SFA. Similarly in previous studies, low n-3 LC-PUFA diets (based on VO) were associated to a higher expression of *srebp1* and/or *fas*, including in gilthead sea bream (Houston et al., 2017), black sea bream (*Spondyliotoma cantharus*) (Jin et al., 2017) or Atlantic Salmon (*Salmo salar*) (Morais et al., 2011). Indeed, the expressions of both genes in the present study were linearly correlated with the dietary n-3 LC-PUFA, particularly with DHA, suggesting that the low dietary contents of these FA are responsible for the up-regulation. The high correlations between the expression of *srebp1* and *fas* and fish hepatocyte size suggest that the increased regulation of these genes in sea bream fed PO might have contributed to the increased lipid deposition in liver resulting in a severe steatosis situation, which is in agreement with previous studies (Morais et al., 2011; Houston et al., 2017).

Additionally, sea bream fed PO diets showed higher contents of palmitoleoyl-CoA (16:1) and oleyl-CoA (18:1), desaturation products of SCD-1a on palmitoyl-CoA (16:0) and stearoyl-CoA (18:0), respectively. The same was true for 18:2n-9, 20:2n-9, 18:3n-6, 20:3n-6, all potential products of FADS2. These results, added to the decreased desaturation index 18:1n-9/18:2n-9 and the highest *scd-1a* and *fads2* expression in these fish, suggest an increased $\Delta 9$ and $\Delta 6$ desaturase activity in response to an EFA-deficiency. These results denote a $\Delta 6$ activity on n-9 FA in gilthead sea bream, as previously suggested (Houston et al., 2017). An *in vivo* up-regulation *fads2* was commonly observed in other marine species fed low EFA-diets, such as meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*) (Carvalho et al., 2018), turbot (*Scophthalmus maximus*) (Owen et al., 1975) or flounder (Lee et al., 2003; Kim and Lee, 2004). However, synthesis of DHA and EPA also requires $\Delta 5$ and, possibly, $\Delta 4$ desaturases in the last steps of the desaturation pathway, which are usually poorly activated in marine species (Tocher, 2015). Thus, the negative impact of PO diets on fish growth and liver health status denoted that the production of LC-PUFA was not sufficient to cover gilthead sea bream essential fatty acid requirements, despite the *fads2* up-regulation. Furthermore, the possible higher activity of *Fads2* on n-9 and n-6 precursors (OA and LA, respectively) rather than on n-3 precursors (ALA) could be probably associated with a lower availability of the latter substrate than the formers, despite the higher affinity of $\Delta 6$ for n-3 fatty acids (Sissener et al., 2017). Interestingly, previous studies also related low dietary n-3 LC-PUFA diets to an up-regulation of *elov15* in marine fish (Carvalho et al., 2018). However, in gilthead sea bream in the present study, *elov15* expression was not significantly up-regulated. These results agree with the minor effect of dietary VO on hepatic expression of *elov15* in a previous study on gilthead sea bream (Houston et al., 2017).

In addition, lipolytic processes seemed less affected by the substitution of FO by PO. LPL is the enzyme responsible for hydrolyzing TAG of lipoproteins making FA available for uptake into organs (Fielding and Frayn, 1998). Previous studies suggested that OA, alone or in combination with LA increased *lpl* expression in liver of red sea bream (*Pragus major*) (Liang et al., 2002), in agreement with the up-regulation tendency of this gene in gilthead sea bream fed 7.5% FM PO of the present study. Indeed, *lpl* expression showed a linear correlation with the dietary OA and LA. Additionally, *cpt1* was up-regulated in these fish. Although several studies suggested a regulatory mechanism of *lpl* and *cpt1* gene expression by PPARs in mammals (Simopoulos, 1996), no significant effects were found in *ppar α* expression in the present study. Both *ppar α* and *cpt1* are two important genes involved in β -oxidation of FA in peroxisomes and mitochondria, respectively, but are regulated by independent pathways (Ayisi et al., 2018). Similarly, in yellow croaker (*Larimichthys crocea*) dietary composition caused no difference in the *ppar α* expression (Dong et al., 2017). However, *ppar α* and/or *cpt1* were down-regulated in gilthead sea bream and Japanese sea bass

(*Lateolabrax japonicus*) in response to low dietary n-3 LC-PUFA (high VO diets), while upregulated in rainbow trout (*Oncorhynchus mykiss*) (Houston et al., 2017; Dong et al., 2017). The discrepancy of these results may indicate that FA β -oxidation can be influenced by several other stimuli rather than only dietary fatty acid composition (Houston et al., 2017).

Few studies have been conducted on the concomitant replacement of FM and FO, some reported an interaction between dietary protein and lipid sources on fish metabolism (Dias et al., 2005, 2009; Benedito-Palos et al., 2007; Torrecillas et al., 2017). In agreement, the concomitant replacement of FM and FO in the present study negatively affected growth performance. This was denoted by the lowest weight in fish fed 7.5% FM compared to those fed 15%. However, little effect of FM level was shown in hepatic indices, liver lipid metabolism associated gene expression or histological status. Furthermore, no interactions were found between the dietary content of FM and lipid source, suggesting that both factors affected independently sea bream performance and metabolism, with FO replacement exerting a much stronger effect than FM content.

5. Conclusions

The present study demonstrates that the total replacement of FO by a blend of microalgae oils, rich in n-3 LC-PUFA, and PO, have no major impact on growth and hepatic lipid metabolism of gilthead sea bream juveniles. In turn, PO as sole source of FO replacement negatively affected fish lipid metabolism, up-regulating lipogenic-related genes (*srebp1* and *fas*), as well as *lpl*. Consequently, these fish showed an increased liver lipid deposition that led to a severe hepatic steatosis and reduced growth. The high dietary contents in n-3 LC-PUFA of FO and microalgae oils diets down-regulated genes involved in FA biosynthetic pathway, including *scd-1a* and *fads2*.

Both protein and lipid sources seemed to independently affect metabolism and performance of fish, with FO replacement exerting a much stronger in lipid metabolism than FM replacement.

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2020.736073>.

Financial support

This study was (partially) funded under EU funded project PerformFISH (Integrating Innovative Approaches for Competitive and Sustainable Performance across the Mediterranean Aquaculture Value Chain) H2020-SFS-2016-2017; 727610. This work was also co-funded by Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información de la Consejería de Economía, Industria, Comercio y Conocimiento and Fondo Social Europeo (FSE) Programa Operativo Integrado de Canarias 2014-2020, Eje 3 Tema Prioritario 74 (85%).

Author agreement/disclosure statement/role of funding sources

The authors wish to confirm that there are no known conflicts of interest associated with this publication and there has been no significant financial support for this work that could have influenced its outcome. We confirm that all data are fully available without restriction. We confirm that the manuscript has been read and approved by all named authors and that there are no other persons who satisfied the criteria for authorship but are not listed. We further confirm that the order of authors listed in the manuscript has been approved by all of us. We confirm that we have given due consideration to the protection of intellectual property associated with this work and that there are no impediments to publication, including the timing of publication, with respect to intellectual property. In so doing we confirm that we have followed the regulations of our institutions concerning intellectual property. We further confirm that any aspect of the work covered in this manuscript that has involved either experimental animals or human

patients has been conducted with the ethical approval of all relevant bodies and that such approvals are acknowledged within the manuscript. We understand that the Corresponding Author is the sole contact for the Editorial process (including Editorial Manager and direct communications with the office). She is responsible for communicating with the other authors about progress, submissions of revisions and final approval of proofs. We confirm that we have provided a current, correct email address which is accessible by the Corresponding Author and which has been configured to accept email from marta.ribeiro101@alu.uplgc.es. We also confirm that the funding sources listed in the present manuscript had no role in study design; in the collection, analysis and interpretation of data; in the writing of the report; and in the decision to submit the article for publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

The authors want to acknowledge Dr. Ramon Fontanillas and Dr. Grethe Rosenlund from Skretting ARC Feed Technology Plant (Stavanger, Norway) for helping in formulation and manufacturing the experimental diets of the present study. The authors also want to express their gratitude to the anonymous reviewers for their help in improving the present manuscript.

References

- Adarme-Vega, T.C., Thomas-Hall, S.R., Schenk, P.M., 2014. Towards sustainable sources for omega-3 fatty acids production. *Curr. Opin. Biotechnol.* 26, 14–18.
- AOAC, 1989. *Official Methods of Analysis*. 17th Edition. The Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Gaithersburg, MD, USA. Methods 925.10, 65.17, 974.24, 992.16.
- Ayisi, C.L., Yamei, C., Zhao, J.L., 2018. Genes, transcription factors and enzymes involved in lipid metabolism in fin fish. *Agri. Gene.* 7, 7–14.
- Benedito-Palos, L., Saera-Vila, A., Caldach-Giner, J.A., Kaushik, S., Pérez-Sánchez, J., 2007. Combined replacement of fish meal and oil in practical diets for fast growing juveniles of gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata* L.): networking of systemic and local components of GH/IGF axis. *Aquaculture* 267 (1–4), 199–212.
- Berge, R.K., Madsen, L., Vaagenes, H., Tronstad, K.J., Gøttlicher, M., Rustan, A.C., 1999. In contrast with docosahexaenoic acid, eicosapentaenoic acid and hypolipidaemic derivatives decrease hepatic synthesis and secretion of triacylglycerol by decreased diacylglycerol acyltransferase activity and stimulation of fatty acid oxidation. *Biochem. J.* 343 (1), 191–197.
- Betancor, M.B., Sprague, M., Montero, D., Usher, S., Sayanova, O., Campbell, P.J., Napier, J.A., Caballero, M.J., Izquierdo, M., Tocher, D.R., 2016. Replacement of marine fish oil with de novo omega-3 oils from transgenic *Camelina sativa* in feeds for gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata* L.). *Lipids* 51 (10), 1171–1191.
- Bradbury, M.W., 2006. Lipid metabolism and liver inflammation. I. Hepatic fatty acid uptake: possible role in steatosis. *Am. J. Physiol. Gastrointest. Liver Physiol.* 290 (2), G194–G198.
- Caballero, M.J., Obach, A., Rosenlund, G., Montero, D., Gisvold, M., Izquierdo, M.S., 2002. Impact of different dietary lipid sources on growth, lipid digestibility, tissue fatty acid composition and histology of rainbow trout, *Oncorhynchus mykiss*. *Aquaculture* 214 (1–4), 253–271.
- Caballero, M.J., Izquierdo, M.S., KjØrsvik, E., Fernández, A., Rosenlund, G., 2004. Histological alterations in the liver of sea bream, *Sparus aurata* L., caused by short- or long-term feeding with vegetable oils. Recovery of normal morphology after feeding fish oil as the sole lipid source. *J. Fish Dis.* 27, 531–541.
- Campos, I., Matos, E., Maia, M.R., Marques, A., Valente, L.M., 2019. Partial and total replacement of fish oil by poultry fat in diets for European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) juveniles: effects on nutrient utilization, growth performance, tissue composition and lipid metabolism. *Aquaculture* 502, 107–120.
- Carvalho, M., Peres, H., Saleh, R., Fontanillas, R., Rosenlund, G., Oliva-Teles, A., Izquierdo, M., 2018. Dietary requirement for n-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids for fast growth of meagre (*Argyrosomus regius*, Asso 1801) fingerlings. *Aquaculture* 488, 105–113.
- Carvalho, M., Montero, D., Rosenlund, G., Fontanillas, R., Ginés, R., Izquierdo, M., 2020. Effective complete replacement of fish oil by combining poultry and microalgae oils in practical diets for gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) fingerlings. *Aquaculture* 529 (in press).
- Cerezuela, R., Guardiola, F.A., Meseguer, J., Esteban, M.A., 2012. Enrichment of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata* L.) diet with microalgae: effects on the immune system. *Fish Physiol. Biochem.* 38 (6), 1729–1739.

- Christie, W.W., 1989. Gas Chromatography and Lipids: A Practical Guide. The Oily Press, Glasgow, UK, 316 pp.
- Cowey, C.B., Sargent, J.R., 1972. Fish nutrition. *Mar. Biol.* 10, 383–492.
- Dias, J., Alvarez, M.J., Arzel, J., Corraze, G., Diez, A., Bautista, J.M., Kaushik, S.J., 2005. Dietary protein source affects lipid metabolism in the European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*). *Comparative Biochem. Physiol. Part A Molec. Integr. Physiol.* 142 (1), 19–31.
- Dias, J., Conceição, L.E., Ribeiro, A.R., Borges, P., Valente, L.M., Dinis, M.T., 2009. Practical diet with low fish-derived protein is able to sustain growth performance in gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) during the grow-out phase. *Aquaculture* 293 (3–4), 255–262.
- Dong, X., Tan, P., Cai, Z., Xu, H., Li, J., Ren, W., Xu, H., Zuo, R., Zhou, J., Mai, K., Ai, Q., 2017. Regulation of FADS2 transcription by SREBP-1 and PPAR- α influences LC-PUFA biosynthesis in fish. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 40024.
- Eryalçın, K., Ganuza, E., Atalah, E., Cruz, M.C.H., 2015. *Nannochloropsis gaditana* and *Cryptocodinium cohnii*, two microalgae as alternative sources of essential fatty acids in early weaning for gilthead seabream. *Hidrobiológica* 25 (2), 193–202.
- European Union, 2010, 33-77. DIRECTIVE 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the council of 22 September 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes. *Off. J. Eur. Union* L276/33.
- Fielding, B.A., Frayn, K.N., 1998. Lipoprotein lipase and the disposition of dietary fatty acids. *Br. J. Nutr.* 80 (6), 495–502.
- Folch, J., Lees, M., Sloane Stanley, G.H., 1957. A simple method for the isolation and purification of total lipids from animal tissues. *J. Biol. Chem.* 226, 497–509.
- Ganuza, E., Izquierdo, M.S., 2007. Lipid accumulation in *Schizochytrium* G13/2S produced in continuous culture. *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 76, 985–990.
- Haas, S., Bauer, J.L., Adakli, A., Meyer, S., Lippemeier, S., Schwarz, K., Schulz, C., 2016. Marine microalgae *Pavlova viridis* and *Nannochloropsis* sp. as n-3 PUFA source in diets for juvenile European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax* L.). *J. Appl. Phycol.* 28 (2), 1011–1021.
- Hatlen, B., Jakobsen, J.V., Crampton, V., Alm, M., Langmyhr, E., Espe, M., Hevrøy, E.M., Torstensen, B.E., Waagbø, R., 2015. Growth, feed utilization and endocrine responses in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) fed diets added poultry by-product meal and blood meal in combination with poultry oil. *Aquac. Nutr.* 21 (5), 714–725.
- Higgs, D.A., Balfry, S.K., Oakes, J.D., Rowshandel, M., Skura, B.J., Deacon, G., 2006. Efficacy of an equal blend of canola oil and poultry fat as an alternate dietary lipid source for Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.) in sea water. I: effects on growth performance, and whole body and fillet proximate and lipid composition. *Aquac. Res.* 37 (2), 180–191.
- Houston, S.J., Karalazos, V., Tinsley, J., Betancor, M.B., Martin, S.A., Tocher, D.R., Monroig, O., 2017. The compositional and metabolic responses of gilthead seabream (*Sparus aurata*) to a gradient of dietary fish oil and associated n-3 long-chain PUFA content. *Br. J. Nutr.* 118 (12), 1010–1022.
- Ibeas, C., Izquierdo, M.S., Lorenzo, A., 1994. Effect of different levels of n-3 highly unsaturated fatty acids on growth and fatty acid composition of juvenile gilthead seabream *Sparus aurata*. *Aquaculture* 127, 177–188.
- Izquierdo, M.S., 1996. Essential fatty acid requirements of cultured marine fish larvae. *Aquac. Nutr.* 2 (4), 183–191.
- Izquierdo, M., 2005. Essential fatty acid requirements in Mediterranean fish species. *Cahiers Options Méditerranéennes* 63, 91–102.
- Izquierdo, M.S., Koven, W., 2011. Lipids. In: Holt, J. (Ed.), *Larval Fish Nutrition*. Wiley-Blackwell, John Wiley and Sons Publisher, Oxford, pp. 47–82.
- Izquierdo, M., Watanabe, T., Takeuchi, T., Arakawa, T., Kitajima, C., 1990. Optimum EPA levels in Artemia to meet the EPA requirements of red seabream (*Pagrus major*). In: Takeda, M., Watanabe, T. (Eds.), *The Current Status of Fish Nutrition in Aquaculture*. Tokyo Univ. Fisheries, Tokyo, pp. 221–232.
- Jiang, Y., Fan, K.W., Tsz-Yeung Wong, R., Chen, F., 2004. Fatty acid composition and squalene content of the marine microalgae *Schizochytrium mangrovei*. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 52 (5), 1196–1200.
- Jin, M., Lu, Y., Yuan, Y., Li, Y., Qiu, H., Sun, P., Ma, H., Ding, L., Zhou, Q.C., 2017. Regulation of growth, antioxidant capacity, fatty acid profiles, hematological characteristics and expression of lipid related genes by different dietary n-3 highly unsaturated fatty acids in juvenile black seabream (*Acanthopagrus schlegelii*). *Aquaculture* 471, 55–65.
- Kim, K.D., Lee, S.M., 2004. Requirement of dietary n-3 highly unsaturated fatty acids for juvenile flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*). *Aquaculture* 229, 315–323.
- Kjaer, M.A., Vegusdal, A., Gjøen, T., Rustan, A.C., Todorović, M., Ruyter, B., 2008. Effect of rapeseed oil and dietary n-3 fatty acids on triacylglycerol synthesis and secretion in Atlantic salmon hepatocytes. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta* 1781, 112–122.
- Kousoulaki, K., Berge, G., Mørkøre, T., Krasnov, A., Baeverfjord, G., Ytrestøl, T., Carlehög, M., Sweetman, J., Ruyter, B., 2020. Microalgal *Schizochytrium limacinum* biomass improves growth and filet quality when used long-term as a replacement for fish oil, in modern salmon diets. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 7, 57.
- Leaver, M.J., Villeneuve, L.A., Obach, A., Jensen, L., Bron, J.E., Tocher, D.R., Taggart, J., 2008. Functional genomics reveals increases in cholesterol biosynthetic genes and highly unsaturated fatty acid biosynthesis after dietary substitution of fish oil with vegetable oils in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*). *BMC Genomics* 9 (1), 299.
- Lee, S.M., Lee, L.H., Kim, K.D., 2003. Effect of dietary essential fatty acids on growth, body composition and blood chemistry of juvenile starry flounder (*Platichthys stellatus*). *Aquaculture* 225, 269–281.
- Liang, X., Oku, H., Ogata, Y.H., Li, Y., Bai, J., Luo, J., 2002. The cDNA sequence and tissue expression of lipoprotein lipase gene of a marine fish, red sea bream (*Pagrus major*). *Chin. J. Biochem. Molec. Biol.* 18 (6), 712–719.
- Liland, N.S., Hatlen, B., Takle, H., Venegas, C., Espe, M., Torstensen, B.E., Waagbø, R., 2015. Including processed poultry and porcine by-products in diets high in plant ingredients reduced liver TAG in Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar* L. *Aquac. Nutr.* 21 (5), 655–669.
- Martoja, R., Martoja-Pierson, M., 1970. *Técnicas de Histología Animal*. Toray-Masson, Barcelona.
- Montero, D., Izquierdo, M., 2010–2011. Welfare and health of fish fed vegetable oils as alternative lipid sources to fish oil. In: Turchini, G., Ng, W., Tocher, D. (Eds.), *Fish oil replacement and alternative lipid sources in aquaculture feeds*. Taylor and Francis, CRC Press, Boca Raton, pp. 439–485.
- Moraes, S., Pratoomyot, J., Taggart, J.B., Bron, J.E., Guy, D.R., Bell, J.G., Tocher, D.R., 2011. Genotype-specific responses in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) subject to dietary fish oil replacement by vegetable oil: a liver transcriptomic analysis. *BMC Genomics* 12 (1), 255.
- Nasopoulou, C., Zabetakis, I., 2012. Benefits of fish oil replacement by plant originated oils in compounded fish feeds. A review. *LWT Food Sci. Technol.* 47 (2), 217–224.
- Naylor, R.L., Hardy, R.W., Bureau, D.P., Chiu, A., Elliott, M., Farrell, A.P., Forster, I., Gatlin, D.M., Goldburg, R.J., Hua, K., Nichols, P.D., 2009. Feeding aquaculture in an era of finite resources. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 106 (36), 15103–15110.
- Owen, J.M., Adron, J.W., Middleton, C., Cowey, C.B., 1975. Elongation and desaturation of dietary fatty acids in turbot *Scophthalmus maximus* L. and rainbow trout *Salmo gairdnerii*. *Rich. Lipids* 10, 528–531.
- Peterson, B.C., Burr, G.S., Barrows, F.T., Block, S., Bowzer, J., Buentello, A., 2019. Growth performance of atlantic salmon smolts fed diets containing heterotrophic algal biomass as replacement of fish oil. *N. Am. J. Aquac.* 81 (4), 364–371.
- Qiao, H., Wang, H., Song, Z., Ma, J., Li, B., Liu, X., Zhang, S., Wang, J., Zhang, L., 2014. Effects of dietary fish oil replacement by microalgae raw materials on growth performance, body composition and fatty acid profile of juvenile olive flounder, *Paralichthys olivaceus*. *Aquac. Nutr.* 20 (6), 646–653.
- Rosenlund, G., Obach, A., Sandberg, M.G., Standal, H., Tveit, K., 2001. Effect of alternative lipid sources on long-term growth performance and quality of Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.). *Aquac. Res.* 32, 323–328.
- Salini, M., Irvin, S., Bourne, N., Blyth, D., Cheers, S., Habilidad, N., Glencross, B., 2015. Marginal efficiencies of long chain-polyunsaturated fatty acid use by barramundi (*Lates calcarifer*) when fed diets with varying blends of fish oil and poultry fat. *Aquaculture* 449, 48–57.
- Santigosa, 2019. Zeroing out the environmental impacts of aquafeed: the Veramaris solution. *Aquafeed Adv. Process. Formul.* 11 (1), 36–39.
- Sarker, P.K., Kapuscinski, A.R., Lanois, A.J., Livesey, E.D., Bernhard, K.P., Coley, M.L., 2016. Towards sustainable aquafeeds: complete substitution of fish oil with marine microalga *Schizochytrium* sp. improves growth and fatty acid deposition in juvenile Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *PLoS One* 11 (6), e0156684.
- Shah, M.R., Lutz, G.A., Alam, A., Sarker, P., Chowdhury, M.K., Parseimehr, A., Liang, Y., Daroch, M., 2018. Microalgae in aquafeeds for a sustainable aquaculture industry. *J. Appl. Phycol.* 30 (1), 197–213.
- Simopoulos, A.P., 1996. The role of fatty acids in gene expression: health implications. *Ann. Nutr. Metab.* 40 (6), 303–311.
- Simopoulos, A.P., 2012. *Health Effects of Polyunsaturated Fatty Acids in Seafoods*. Academic Press, p. 472.
- Sissener, N.H., Sanden, M., Torstensen, B.E., Waagbø, R., Stubhaug, I., Rosenlund, G., 2017. High dietary 18: 2n-6/18: 3n-3 ratio does not inhibit elongation and desaturation of 18: 3n-3 to EPA and DHA in Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar* L.). *Aquac. Nutr.* 23 (5), 899–909.
- Spanish Government, 2005. REAL DECRETO 1201/2005, de 10 de octubre, sobre protección de los animales utilizados para experimentación y otros fines científicos. *BOE núm.* 252, 34367–34391.
- Spisni, E., Tugnoli, M., Ponticelli, A., Mordenti, T., Tomasi, V., 1998. Hepatic steatosis in artificially fed marine teleosts. *J. Fish Dis.* 21, 177–184.
- Tibaldi, E., Zittelli, G.C., Parisi, G., Bruno, M., Giorgi, G., Tulli, F., Venturini, S., Tredici, M.R., Poli, B.M., 2015. Growth performance and quality traits of European sea bass (*D. labrax*) fed diets including increasing levels of freeze-dried *Isochrysis* sp. (T-ISO) biomass as a source of protein and n-3 long chain PUFA in partial substitution of fish derivatives. *Aquaculture* 440, 60–68.
- Tocher, D.R., 2015. Omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids and aquaculture in perspective. *Aquaculture* 449, 94–107.
- Tocher, D.R., Betancor, M.B., Sprague, M., Olsen, R.E., Napier, J.A., 2019. Omega-3 long-chain polyunsaturated fatty acids, EPA and DHA: bridging the gap between supply and demand. *Nutrients* 11 (1), 89.
- Torrecillas, S., Robaina, L., Caballero, M.J., Montero, D., Calandra, G., Mompel, D., Karalazos, V., Kaushik, S., Izquierdo, M.S., 2017. Combined replacement of fishmeal and fish oil in European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*): production performance, tissue composition and liver morphology. *Aquaculture* 474, 101–112.
- Tukey, J.W., 1949. Comparing individual means in the analysis of variance. *Biometrics* 99–114.
- Turchini, G.M., Torstensen, B.E., Ng, W.K., 2009. Fish oil replacement in finfish nutrition. *Rev. Aquac.* 1 (1), 10–57.
- Turchini, G.M., Hermon, K., Cleveland, B.J., Emery, J.A., Rankin, T., Francis, D.S., 2013. Seven fish oil substitutes over a rainbow trout grow-out cycle: (I) Effects on performance and fatty acid metabolism. *Aquac. Nutr.* 19, 82–94.
- Verreth, J., Coppoolse, J., Segner, H., 1994. The effect of low HUFA- and high HUFA enriched Artemia, fed at different feeding levels, on growth, survival, tissue fatty acids and liver histology of *Clarias gariepinus* larvae. *Aquaculture* 126, 137–150.
- Vizcaíno, A.J., López, G., Sáez, M.I., Jiménez, J.A., Barros, A., Hidalgo, L., Camacho-Rodríguez, J., Martínez, T.F., Cerón-García, M.C., Alarcón, F.J., 2014. Effects of the

- microalga *Scenedesmus almeriensis* as fishmeal alternative in diets for gilthead sea bream, *Sparus aurata*, juveniles. *Aquaculture* 431, 34–43.
- Watanabe, T., 1993. Importance of docosahexaenoic acid in marine larval fish. *J. World Aquacult. Soc.* 24 (2), 152–161.
- Zhang, K., Li, H., Chen, W., Zhao, M., Cui, H., Min, Q., Wang, H., Chen, S., Li, D., 2017. Regulation of the docosapentaenoic acid/docosahexaenoic acid ratio (DPA/DHA ratio) in *Schizochytrium limacinum* B4D1. *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.* 182 (1), 67–81.